

Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of *p,p'*-[Bis-(4-aryl-3-chloro-2-azetidinon-1-yl)]-Diphenylsulphones and Di-*m*-tolyl

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Some new *p,p'*-[bis-(4-aryl-3-chloro-2-azetidinon-1-yl)]-diphenylsulphones and di-*m*-tolyl have been prepared. The constitution of the products was supported by ir spectra. The products were screened for antibacterial activity.

β -Lactum derivatives are most widely prescribed antibiotics in medicine¹. 2-Azetidinone derivatives possess wide therapeutic activity, viz. sedative, hypnotic, anticonvulsant², herbicidal³ and antibacterial⁴. *p,p'*-Diaminodiphenylsulphone possesses antibacterial⁵ and antimalarial activity⁶. *o*-Tolidine derivatives also show bacteriostatic⁷ and antifungal⁸ activity. With a view to prepare better therapeutic agents, we have prepared *p,p'*-[bis-(4-aryl-3-chloro-2-azetidinon-1-yl)]-diphenylsulphone and di-*m*-tolyl by the condensation of chloroacetylchloride with Schiff bases^{9,10} obtained from different aldehydes with *p,p'*-diaminodiphenylsulphone and *o*-tolidine. The constitution of the product was supported by ir spectra¹¹. The ir spectra (KBr) of *p,p'*-[bis-(4-phenyl-3-chloro-2-azetidinon-1-yl)]-diphenylsulphone I showed bands at 1150 ($-\text{SO}_2-$), 1710 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ of β -lactum) and 750 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{Cl}$ stretch). The spectra (KBr) of *p,p'*-[bis-(4-phenyl-3-chloro-2-azetidinon-1-yl)]-di-*m*-tolyl (II) showed bands at 1730 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ β -lactum) and 750 ($\text{C}-\text{Cl}$ stretch). The products were screened for antimicrobial activity.

(I)

(II)

R = Aryl

Experimental

Preparation of *p,p'*-[bis-(4-phenyl-3-chloro-2-azetidinon-1-yl)]-diphenylsulphone: To well stirred solution of *p,p'*-bis-(benzalamino-phenyl)-sulphone (0.01

mol) and triethylamine (0.02 mol) in dry dioxan (50 ml) was added monochloroacetylchloride (0.02 mol) dropwise at room temperature and the mixture was stirred for 5 h and left at room temperature for three days. The precipitate of triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered and washed with dioxane. The filtrate was treated with dried magnesium sulphate and the product was crystallised from ethanol to yield I (Found: C, 62.41; H, 3.85; N, 4.81; Cl, 12.35. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{22}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$ required C, 62.39; H, 3.81; N, 4.85; Cl, 12.30%). Similarly other Schiff bases from *o*-tolidine were condensed with monochloroacetyl chloride to get azetidinones of type II.

Antibacterial activity: The compounds were tested for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* by disk method¹² using ethanol as a solvent at a concentration of 10 mg ml^{-1} . The test solution containing 0.5 mg was used. From the experimental data it was observed that all compounds showed good activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. The antibacterial activity is not better as compared to the well known antibiotics.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS OF *p,p'*-BIS-(4-ARYL-3-CHLORO-2-AZETIDINON-2-YL)-DIPHENYLSULPHONES (I)*

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Diameter of zone of inhibition mm	
				<i>S. aureus</i> 24 h	<i>E. coli</i> 24 h
1.	Phenyl	193	79	20	21
2.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	137	55	23	22
3.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	126	61	27	20
4.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	145	69	21	19
5.	3-Bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	140	71	24	20
6.	3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	135	85	24	19
7.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	155	76	20	20
8.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	168	69	24	20
9.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	161	77	25	27
10.	α -Furfuryl	180	79	27	24

* All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS OF *p,p'*-BIS-(4-ARYL-3-CHLORO-2-AZETIDINON-1-YL)-DI-*m*-TOLYL (II)*

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Diameter of zone of inhibition mm	
				<i>S. aureus</i> 24 h	<i>E. coli</i> 24 h
1.	Phenyl	265	81	28	24
2.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	268	65	34	30
3.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	275	72	35	29
4.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	284	69	36	31
5.	3-Bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	258	76	42	38
6.	3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	209	85	44	41
7.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	250	61	43	30
8.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	268	55	44	31
9.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	265	64	44	30
10.	α -Furfuryl	275	71	41	21

* All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

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